

Towards a Method for Automatic Detection of Textual Comparisons. A DH-Case Study on the Construction of “Swissness”

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Introduction

The concept ‘national literature’ presupposes and co-constructs distinct ‘literatures’ and invites their comparison across co-constructed ‘nations’ (Anderson, 1998). In German-Swiss literary discourse from 1850-1950, the (self-)conceptualization of ‘Swiss’ nationality and the shifting relationship to its neighboring countries are specifically challenged. Conceptualizing a corpus of texts *about* literature, our paper examines implicit textual practices and semantics of comparing (Epple et al., 2020) that evoke different practices of comparing and evaluation.

Practices of comparing relate two or more *comparata* to each other, conveying a *tertium comparationis* – e.g., when comparing the comparata ‘apples’ to ‘pears’, one conventional tertium is ‘fruits’. Textual comparisons cover a broad range between implicit and explicit forms of comparing. In our CLS research project, we compressed a scale of 5 grades of explicitness (Davy et al. 2019) to a binary opposition: we consider sentences as either explicit comparisons or implicit comparisons. We define implicit comparisons as language use that states something about *comparata* without addressing any similarity/dissimilarity relation within the utterance itself.

In this proof-of-concept study, we focus on implicit comparisons in literary histories: We assume that creating and delineating literary production as ‘national’ was enabled by the networked usage of ‘national literature’ as an over-

arching *tertium*. It follows that single-sentence statements about a national entity may be considered part of a vast network of comparisons spanning works about literature. Implicit comparisons rely strongly on the situative, material, and discursive context, which complicates algorithmic detection. We address this challenge by considering single utterances as part of networked implicit, intratextual, or supra-textual formations of comparing that are dynamically initiated by the construction of ‘national literature’ (Hillebrandt 2014, p. 103-4). Our vantage point for formalized identification of implicit comparisons is their evaluative dimension in the ‘national’ literary history ‘around 1900’: not only do these longer texts feature comparisons at sentence level that are likely to be implicit and evaluative.

To detect potential implicit comparisons, we combine rule-based entity detection and manual annotation with a deep learning approach to sentiment analysis: (1) identification of discrete entities as potential *comparata* based on a lexicon of nation-related entities; (2) manual annotation of the resulting sentences for *valence* (for reasons of focus, ‘explicit comparison’ sentences will not be addressed in the present paper, but will be subject of further studies). (3) we use the annotated data to train a deep learning sentiment classifier.

We utilize sentiment analysis as a marker of evaluative assessment of discourse entities: The evaluative dimension of text can be made visible by looking at the sentences’ *valence*, detected by sentiment analysis (SA), a process for quantifying the subjective and emotional undercurrent in a given text (Lei and Liu, 2021). It finds wide application in recent studies in Computational Literary Studies (Grisot and Herrmann, 2023; Salgaro, 2023; Vlachos and Husen, 2023), where many studies classify ‘*valence*’ on a positive/neutral/negative axis (cf. Kim and Klinger, 2019). Approaches to computing sentiment range from dictionary-based ones to deep learning (Lighear, Catal, and Tekinerdogan, 2021). By expanding the analysis to sentences, we test and expand the obtained results.

We aim to provide a first step into the operationalization of textual manifestations of comparison for a mixed-methods approach, following the typology provided in the works of the CRC1288, especially Davy et al 2019, Kramer et al 2020, Epple et al 2020. More information on the full project can be found on <https://www.uni-bielefeld.de/sfb/sfb1288/projektbereiche/e06/>. The annotation guidelines, code, and the data can be found here: https://github.com/DanielKababgi/Swissness_Comparison/.

The contributions of this paper are threefold: (1) we develop an annotation process for *valence* of implicit comparisons; (2) evaluate a method for detecting implicit value assessment for relevant nation-related entities; and (3) perform a pilot study into the usage of implicit comparisons in the valuation of ‘Swiss’ and other nations in a corpus of German-Swiss literary histories in between Federal state foundation and the end of the Second World War.

Data

We created a corpus consisting of eleven academic works about Swiss literature, published in German 1861-1951, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Current corpus of literary histories, ranging from 1861 to 1951.

Year	Author	Title	N Sentences	N Tokens	Place, Publisher
1861	Mürkofer	Die Schweizerische Literatur des achtzehnten Jahrhunderts	7586	172934	Leipzig, Hirzel
1866	Weber	Die poetische Nationalliteratur der deutschen Schweiz; Musterstücke aus den Dichtungen der besten schweizerischen Schriftsteller von Haller bis auf die Gegenwart, mit biographischen und kritischen Einleitungen	11035	145046	Glarus, Vogel
1892	Bächtold	Geschichte der deutschen Literatur in der Schweiz	30557	398525	Frauenfeld, Huber
1910	Jenny/Rosset	Geschichte der schweizerischen Literatur	9616	167673	Bern, Francke
1914	Frey	Schweizer Dichter	2742	55839	Leipzig, Quelle & Meyer
1918	Korrodi	Schweizerische Literaturbriefe.	804	15106	Frauenfeld, Huber
1924	Korrodi	Schweizerdichtung der Gegenwart	906	17433	Leipzig, Haessel
1924	Nadler	Der geistige Aufbau der deutschen Schweiz (1798-1848)	817	18384	Leipzig, Haessel
1933	Ermatinger	Dichtung und Geistesleben der deutschen Schweiz	15312	280703	München, Beck
1943	Korrodi	Geisteserbe der Schweiz. Schriften von Albrecht von Haller bis zur Gegenwart	5316	109865	Zürich, Rentsch
1951	Zäch	Die Dichtung der deutschen Schweiz	3426	66301	Zürich, Speer

It is important to note that while this corpus is comprehensive for the period and text type, it is not a representative sample of the ‘German-Swiss literary discourse’ as a whole. Any results obtained will be assertions about a set of ‘literary histories’ as a historically situated text type, reflecting the included authors’/publishers’ perspectives, and do not assess historical change in a more general way. This study on literary histories however provides a starting point, with N=1.44 mio words and N=88,116 sentences, being situated in between a qualitative and a quantitative analysis.

Method

For the automatic detection of nation-related references, we split all texts into single sentences and use a lexical approach to select the relevant ones. To operationalize nation-related *comparata*, we created a ‘whitelist’ containing names of countries, cities, and synonyms. Sentences containing such an entity were selected for analysis. Out of

roughly N= 8,000 filtered sentences, n= 2,000 randomized sentences were used, assuring a matching distribution between random sample and complete dataset. After dropping all false-positive matches, n=1,655 sentences remained. These were then manually annotated sentences, the rest were automatically annotated with the deep learning classifier. Fig. 1 shows the count of occurrences of sentences with nation-related entities in our dataset:

Fig 1: Frequency of Nation of manual annotation and automatic annotation

Figure 1: Occurrences of sentences with nation-related entities in (A) the dataset for manual annotation, and (B) the dataset for automatic annotation.

Since only Switzerland, Germany, and France are referenced frequently, the following analysis focuses on the evaluative assessment of those nations. An overview of the relative distribution of sentences containing nation-related entities can be seen in Fig 2:

Fig 2: Frequency of Nations (DEU, CHE, FRA) in all sentences

Figure 2: Relative frequency of CHE, DEU, and FRA in both the datasets for manual and automatic annotation.

As was expected from a corpus of Swiss literary histories, references to Switzerland are dominant (and over time appear to slightly rise). The proportion of references to Germany is relatively stable (but appears to slightly drop). Some oscillations are visible regarding France, but they

may be quite clearly attributed to the bi-lingual two-tome publication by Jenny/Rossell, and Korrodi’s 1918 book. It remains to be seen in future analyses, whether diachronic trends more generally may be observed.

Assuming that in literary histories, lexical evocation of the ‘national dimension’ indicates a potential comparison, statements without explicit markers of comparison (e.g., “verglichen mit”, “ist schöner als”) were considered as potential context-based ‘implicit comparisons’. Those sentences were annotated for valence on a categorical scale, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Examples of different valences.

Valence	Example
+2	“Amiel [...] war entzückt, gerührt, ergriffen.”
+1	“Er wirkte redlich mit, die Poesie der Engländer und der Alten zum Gemeingute der deutschen Nation zu machen.”
0	“Später wandte er sich nach München.”
-1	“Das Machtbedürfnis der Kantone [...] rüchte sich durch Schikanen im Inneren und durch den tippigen Emportrieb nörgelnden Philistergeistes und öder Fraubaserei, die in den kleinen Verhältnissen der Schweiz immer gedeihen.”
-2	“Ganz arm ist die Schweiz des siebzehnten Jahrhunderts an Werken der Prosa, die in den Bereich der Literaturgeschichte fallen würden.”

The n= 2,000 randomly selected sentences were annotated by two sets of annotators, achieving an Intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC31) of 0.55, with a lower bound of 0.52 and an upper bound of 0.58 for the 95% confidence interval. The moderate reliability (add ref to Landis / Koch 1977, p. 165), which given the historical alterity and complexity of the scientific prose, is a good basis for continued analysis.

A deep learning classifier was trained on the manually annotated data. We reduced the number of categories from five to three (-1, 0, +1), corresponding to negative, neutral, or positive sentiment. Using the gbert-large model by Depset (Chan et al., 2020) as input for the multi-class classification head, we achieved a final F1 score of 0.5921. Further thoughts about this score are given in the discussion.

To analyze evaluative assessment of nation-related references, we used the trained model to compute the valence of each sentence contributing to the text-spanning networked implicit comparisons. We utilized the manually annotated valence data to (1) discern the evaluative assessment of ‘national references’ in the comparative statements, (2) to evaluate automatic sentiment analysis for previously unseen texts with the same goal.

Fig 3: Distribution of Valence of manual annotation and automatic annotation

Figure 3: Distribution of valence for manual in white and automatic annotation in red for CHE, DEU, and FRA.

The distribution of valence for the manually annotated data and the results of the automatic classifier are shown in Fig 3. The results show similar distributions with some slight differences. These can be explained by the different sets and amounts of sentences in the datasets. The means of the distributions are very similar, and in both datasets Switzerland and Germany have slightly positive sentiment compared to neutral sentiment for France. To evaluate the method more formally, we use a ranked-sum Wilcoxon test and compare the valence distributions between the individual nations for the manually and automatically annotated data. The results are shown respectively in Fig 4 (A) and (B).

For both datasets the differences between Switzerland and Germany are not statistically significant, which corresponds to the trend depicted in Fig 3. For the manually annotated dataset neither the differences between France and the two other nations, respectively, are statistically significant. For the automatically annotated dataset, both the distributions of FRA are highly significantly different from CHE and DEU. The trend seen in the manually annotated dataset could not be replicated fully in the automatically annotated dataset.

Fig 4: Statistical differences of distribution of valence between manual annotation and automatic annotation

Figure 4: Statistical differences of distribution of valence between (A) manual annotation and (B) automatic annotation for CHE, DEU, and FRA.

Figure 5: Mean of valence for sentences containing a nation-related entity per literary history for manual and automatic annotation.

As Fig 5 shows, positive valuation of Switzerland, Germany, and especially France is generally increasing in our corpus in both datasets. These findings may very cautiously be interpreted: The initially negative valuation of Germany and France may indicate a tendency to differentiate ‘Swiss culture’ from that of other countries after the Bundestaatsgründung in 1848. Negative sentiment towards French culture might be attributed to both countries’ strained relationship during the 19th Century. The overall neutral and later on positive valuation towards German culture might be explained by the linguistic, historical, and cultural proximity of both countries. The rapid increase of positive sentiment towards France after 1933 can be related to the ‘Geistige Landesverteidigung’ (Mooser, 1997; Jorio, 2006; Sandberg, 2007) against The Third Reich, propagating positivity towards non-German neighbors, and to the intention to strengthen Switzerland from within by integrating the German-speaking parts with its other language communities. Striking is the increasing positive valuation of Germany despite the Geistige Landesverteidigung. This might be due to individual authors’ preference to seek closeness to Germany and/or The Third Reich. Both points will be further tested against a planned larger dataset.

Our approach produces insights regarding the diachronic distant reading perspective. The analyzed sentences are also viable candidates for close reading, examining comparison type and rhetorical strategies. Our method yields findings that can be assessed further. E.g., the following sentences identified by the classifier show attributions and valuations made by the different authors with regard to the different nations:

“Mit scharfem Verstand erkennt und faßt der Schweizer sein Ziel, wählt mit ruhiger Umsicht die Mittel zu demselben und erreicht es durch Entschlossenheit und zähe Willenskraft.” (Mörkofer 1861, 50)

“Die reiche und große Natur der Schweiz regte daher vor Allem die Natur Forschung an und bildete und erzog zu allen Zeiten berühmte Natur forscher, unter de-

nen Konrad Geßner, Scheuchzer, Haller u.s.w. nicht nur Zierden der Wissenschaft, sondern auch des ganzen Vaterlandes sind.” (Mörkofer 1861, 58)

Discussion and Outlook

It is important to note that the moderate ICC (0.55) points to some remaining issues with the annotation guidelines and the data. Some sentences prove especially difficult to classify by our annotators, due to the difficulty of the elevated style and historicity of corpus. The following sentences were annotated both as positive and negative. Depending on their context and the readers’ perspective, both interpretations can be seen as viable:

“Auf diesem schattenlosen Voten nun trinkt man des Morgens die Ziegenmolken oder Geißschotten, wie die Schweizer sprechen, die täglich aus dem Gebirge drei Stunden weit noch ganz heiß gebracht wird, sofern es wahr ist, dass sie nicht unterwegs gewärmt werde - und bratet dabei an der Sonne, deren Strahlen nun schon wieder brennen, als könnte es hier nie Winter werden.” (Weber 1866, 15693)

“Während sonst die Dichter jener Zeit sich den Preis der Fürsten zur Aufgabe machten, so singt der Schweizer die Eitelkeit äußerer Größe, und während jene Dichter sich mit ihren Reimen den Großen der Erde zu Füßen legen, kennt Haller keine höhere Befriedigung als das Glück seines Freundes und den treuen Freundschaftsbund mit ihm.” (Mörkofer 1861, 396)

Similar problems arise from sentences containing multiple entities and subjects. Depending on the entity focalized, sentiment can vary widely:

“Es gibt keinen Lyriker der Schweiz und in Deutschland nur sehr wenige, die ihn [Leuthold] an virtuoser Herrschaft über die Sprache und an Wohlklang der Verse erreichen.” (Ermatinger 1933, 81596)

Still, the method for operationalizing implicit comparisons renders promising results, pointing to a contrast in the evaluation of national comparata by language, with the German-speaking countries on the one hand and especially France on the other. Additionally, the preliminary diachronic analysis may indicate a tendency of valuating German entities more positively than Swiss ones, which is surprising and needs more analysis on qualitative and quantitative grounds.

Our approach yielded various interpretable data, yet will be refined iteratively. The identification of a large amount of nation-related comparisons proved to work. The whitelist approach for finding relevant sentences is easily implemented and expanded, but may be made more effective.

Provided more analyses, our manual and explorative approaches thus pave the road for further applying and refining the taxonomy proposed by the CRC1288. The next steps include expanding our corpus, operationalizing expli-

citiness of comparisons, and assessing the tertium comparationis employed, enabling more fine-grained analysis focused on diachronic differences.

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